

Carbon-13 Nmr Signals of some Simple Coumarins[†]

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Carbon-13 nmr spectra of some simple coumarins related to osthol (1) are reported.

OSTHOL (1) is one of the common coumarins occasionally found from natural sources. In recent years osthol and its epoxide (5) have been employed for some interesting transformation studies¹⁻⁸. This communication reports the carbon-13 nmr spectral data for osthol (1) and some of its derivatives (2-6 and 10) along with those of the related compounds phebalosin (7) and ulopterol (8). The spectrum of umbelliferone methyl ether⁹ ($\equiv$ 7-methoxycoumarin) was used as a model. Incidentally 6 as well as the *laevo* antipodes of 4 and 5 have also been reported from natural sources¹⁰ and designated citrusal, meranzin hydrate and meranzin ($\equiv$ auraptene), respectively. *Dextro* form of meranzine hydrate acetate (10) has also been found from plants¹⁰.

The coumarin carbons in osthol (1) and its derivatives 2 and 3 resonate more or less in similar positions. A comparison of these resonance positions (Table 1) with the carbon-13 resonances of umbelliferone methyl ether (9) indicates that the alkyl side chain at C-8 in 1-3 causes strong deshielding at C-8 ($\sim$ 16.9-18.8 ppm) along with marginal shielding of both C-7 and C-8a ($\sim$ 1.9-2.3 and 2.6-3.0 ppm, respectively probably by γ -effects with C-2') as well as of C-5 (by $\sim$ 2.2-2.4 ppm). The methyl of the methoxy group in 1-3 is pushed towards C-6 causing the shielding (γ -effect) of the latter $\sim$ 5.4-5.5 ppm relative to similar carbon in 9. Phebalosin (7) also exhibits coumarin carbon resonances similar to those of 4-6.

(3)

(4) R=H
(10) R=COCH₃

(5)

(6)

(7)

(8)

(1)

(2)

A differentiation between the resonance positions of C-4a and C-8 in 1-3 was made in the following way. The non-protonated sp² carbon signal at δ 117.4 in 1, undergoing minor shifts in the spectra of 2 and 3, moves upfield by about 3.5 ppm in the spectra of 4, 5 and 10. This is due to the shielding γ -effect of the oxygen functions at C-2' in 4, 5 and 10 exhibited on C-8. This study indicates that the

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TABLE 1—CARBON-13 NMR SIGNALS (δ) OF THE SIMPLE COUMARINS (1—10)

Carbon	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
C-2	160.9	161.3	161.3	160.7 ^a	160.7 ^a	160.7 ^a	161.6	161.2	160.5	160.6 ^a
C-3	112.4	112.8	112.6	112.7	112.7	112.9	113.0	112.5	112.1	112.2
C-4	143.5	143.7	143.7	143.7	143.5	143.6	143.2	143.4	142.9	143.6
C-4a	112.6	112.8	112.7	112.6	112.6	113.9	112.5	111.7	112.2	112.2
C-5	126.0	125.9	126.1	126.8	127.0	127.3	128.8	129.4	128.8	126.8
C-6	107.1	107.1	107.2	107.2	107.2	107.2	107.4	120.2	112.6	106.8
C-7	159.9	160.3	160.1	160.5 ^a	160.5 ^a	160.3 ^a	160.0	160.6	162.2	160.2 ^a
C-8	117.4	119.3	118.6	113.9	113.9	114.7	112.2	98.4	100.5	114.1
C-8a	152.4	152.8	152.7	153.1	153.1	^b	153.6	154.4	155.4	152.8
C-1'	21.6	20.5	17.5	25.8	22.2	30.0	51.5	32.3	—	22.8
C-2'	120.9	38.	042.3	78.0	62.7	47.2	60.3	77.2	—	78.5
C-3'	132.1	28.	170.7	72.7	59.0	204.8	141.1	72.7	—	71.6
C-4'	25.4	22.4	28.8	25.3	29.8	21.3	113.1	26.0	—	25.6
C-5'	17.5	22.4	28.8	23.9	18.8	21.3	17.1	23.3	—	25.0
OOH ₂	55.7	55.9	55.9	55.9	55.9	55.6	56.1	55.7	—	55.6
COOH ₂	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	169.9
COOH ₂	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	20.1

^a Assignments are interchangeable. ^b C-8a resonance was ill-resolved from noise.

C-4a and C-8 resonance assignments of osthol (1), made earlier by Wenkert *et al.*¹¹, should be reversed.

The resonance assignments of the alkyl side chain carbons in 1-8 and 10 (Table 1), were made from the change in their resonance positions in the spectra of these compounds. The methylene carbon signal at δ 21.6 present in the spectrum of 1 is obviously related to C-1'. The olefinic methine carbon signal at δ 120.9 and non-protonated sp² carbon signal at δ 132.1 in 1 are missing in the spectrum of 2 indicating their association with C-2' and C-3', respectively in 1. The methyl groups resonate at δ 17.5 and 25.4. The former signal was related to C-5' since it suffers *cis* interaction with the methylene group and is thus expected¹² to experience some shielding effect.

The methine (C-3') and methyl carbon (C-4' and C-5') signals in 2 are readily identified from the splitting pattern of the signals in the SFORD spectrum. The methylene carbons (C-1' and C-2') resonate at δ 20.5 and 38.0. C-2' in 2 should resonate at lower field than C-1' since the former experiences more deshielding α - and β -effects¹². The assignment receives support from the following observation. The attachment of a hydroxyl function at C-3' as in 3 causes downfield shift of the signal at δ 38.0 in 2 to δ 42.3 in 3 and upfield shift of the resonance at δ 20.5 in 2 to δ 17.5 in 3. Since in 3, C-1' should experience shielding γ -effect of OH function whereas C-2' should undergo downfield shift for the presence of OH on adjacent carbon (by β -effect) C-1' and C-2' in 3 are related to the signals at δ 17.5 and 42.3, respectively. Additional support to the above assignments is obtained from inspections of the spectra of 4, 5 and 10. The methylene signals present at δ 25.8, 22.2 and 22.8 in 4, 5 and 10, respectively, are undoubtedly associated with C-1' in these compounds. The relatively low field positions of these signals compared to C-1' resonance in 3 (at δ 17.5) are in conformity with that C-1' in 4 as well as in 5 and 10 experience additional deshielding effect of

the oxygen function at C-2'. In 5, the methyl (C-5') eclipsed (or so) with methylene (C-1') should resonate at higher field. The resonances for C-1' to C-5' in 6 are assignable from the splitting pattern in the SFORD spectrum.

The side chain carbon resonance assignments of phebalosin (7) follow from comparison with similar carbon resonances in 2 and 5. Compound 4 as well as (+)-ulopterol¹³ (8) have the same alkyl side chain which exerts more or less similar deshielding effect ($\sim$ 12.6-13.4 ppm) on C-8 or C-6 as appropriate. In 8, methyl of the methoxy group is likely to be pushed towards C-8. The magnitude of shielding ($\sim$ 2.1 ppm) of C-8 in 8 relative to 9 was, however, somewhat less than that observed for C-6 in 1-7.

The hydroxyl at C-3' in 3 causes (relative to 2) strong deshielding of C-3' by $\sim$ 42.6 ppm, significant deshielding of C-2' ($\sim$ 4.3 ppm) as well as of C-4' and C-5' ($\sim$ 6.4 ppm). It exerts $\sim$ 3.0 ppm shielding effect on C-1'. The hydroxyl function at C-2' in 4 deshields C-2' (35.7 ppm), C-1' (8.3 ppm) as well as C-3' (2.0 ppm) and shields C-4' and C-5' by about 3.5 and 4.9 ppm, respectively, when compared with the respective carbon resonances in 3.

Experimental

The carbon-13 nmr spectra were recorded on Varian Associates CFT-20 NMR spectrometer operating at 20 MHz in the FT mode. The compounds were submitted to proton-noise decoupling and single frequency off-resonance decoupling to establish carbon shifts and degree of protonation. The samples were run in 5 mm (o.d.) tubes using CDCl₃ as solvent as well as internal lock. The spectra were taken with sweep width 4000 Hz (4500 Hz for 6), a pulse of approximately 45° flip angle and about 3 s delay between pulses. All solutions were about 5-15% in concentration. The solvent signal was used as internal standard. The

chemical shifts reported are in δ (ppm) downfield from TMS ($\delta_{\text{TMS}} = \delta_{\text{CDCl}_3} + 76.9$ ppm).

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